

The Process Of Developing Leadership Competencies For High School Principals - Insights From Vietnamese Case

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Abstract

In the context of globalization and international integration in the field of education and training in Vietnam, modern theories of leadership development for principals of high schools have been approached and applied in both training of administrators and school leadership practices. This study was conducted to help clarify the question of how the theories of school leadership development from the point of view of Western authors can be compatible in the context of high school policy and leadership culture in Vietnam. From the results of that assessment, the authors have connected the theoretical foundations with the practice of school leadership to propose some solutions to optimize the theories of leadership development in cultivating and training principals of high schools in Vietnam.

Introduction

Many researchers about leadership capacity and leadership capacity developments for high school principals in Vietnam were conducted. Most of these studies have focused on identifying the diverse processes of professional development that are conducted annually to support and develop leadership capacity for educational administrators - an important factor in determining the quality of education. In practice, most principals in Vietnam are cultivated and developed from the teaching staff, with the principal term's duration at high school being limited by the number of years, which is usually 5 years each management term. If the career of high school principals were based on the roadmap, the maturity of their management and leadership capabilities associated with each stage of their career can be observed. From there, the school leadership capacity at each stage in the career will have different effects depending on the compatibility of the principal's experience, attitude, and conditions based on policy and culture. The career development process of most high school principals in Vietnam can be described as follows:

Figure 1: Career development process of high school principals in Vietnam

In the context of globalization and international integration in the field of education and training in Vietnam, modern theories of leadership development for principals of high schools have been approached and applied in both schools and training administrators as well as practical school leaders. Theories of school leadership development from the point of view of Western authors gradually became compatible and are promoted in the context of cultural characteristics and policies in Vietnam. This study evaluated the opinions of 295 principals from high schools in Vietnam about the practice of training and developing school leadership capacity. From the

results of that assessment, the authors of the study have connected the theoretical foundations with the practice of school leadership to propose solutions that can optimize the theories of leadership development in the practice of cultivating and training principals of high schools in Vietnam. This study aims to answer the following questions:

- (1) How are the modern theories of the leadership development process of school principals concretized in the context of the current policy and culture of Vietnam?
- (2) Proposing recommendations to develop leadership capacity for high school principals in Vietnam.

Literature review

OECD's research about leader development programs found out that the role of school leadership changed significantly in recent years. High school principals have a greater responsibility not only in school management but also in maintaining pedagogical quality. To respond to these changes effectively, thorough preparation and appropriate training are required for current and future school leaders (Pont et al., 2008, Chapter 3).

Experts in leadership and professional development believed that training and retraining activities for school principals should be carried out continuously and hierarchically according to each career stage. (Davis et al., 2005; Pont et al., 2008, Chapter 3; Schleicher, 2012, Chapter 1).

These activities need to be built on the legacy of previous stages of learning and continued throughout the stages of a leadership career. Effective leadership development begins with the teacher and continues for the principal candidate stage and to principals in the first year of their term so that the process becomes continuous and adaptive.

In Tony Bush's research regarding the performance of newly appointed principals, it was believed that to lead effectively, principals need to be aware of "the increasing complexities of the school context, combining with the trend of online management, has increased the need for the leadership preparation of the principal". It was also stated that this preparation should be a process of adapting to new requirements from the context, which is not always easy (Bush, 2008, Chapter 3).

Frost and Durant assessed that the development of leadership thinking should go beyond to reach the level of seeing the school as a learning organization and that the principal needs to learn both on the spot and through the daily school leadership activities rather than focusing solely on developing training programs or other interventions. Such development is related to how attitudes are fostered, how activities are carried out to develop through leadership, and that the learning organization needs to be continuously encouraged to develop effective leadership for principals. (Bush, 2008, Chapter 4).

Theoretical perspective

Leadership capacity:

Leadership capacity plays an important and decisive role in the performance of each school. In recent years, there have been studies that clarify the nature of leadership capacity by pointing out the component competencies that must be expressed in the cultural context of both the school itself and its community.

Duffy assessed that leadership capacity is a combination of knowledge, skills, abilities, and behaviors that demonstrates outstanding performance (Duffy, 2009). It is clear that successful school leadership is not about achieving a position in the school, but more about using the knowledge and skills learned to build and develop a successful school, with the success of a principal being measured by the success of the school itself. Hence, "School leaders need impressive skills to provide effective leadership in our diverse school environments" (Sharma, 2011). Farah (2013) emphasizes that the principal of a school is like the manager of any organization, who is also a politician, an economist, a psychologist, and a sociologist. The principal, first and foremost, is a pillar of the school, who plays an important role in the development of school programs based on properly assessing the needs and characteristics of their students, which requires principals to have skills in managing and developing educational programs. Besides, principals need to be able to interact with others to not only bring members of the school together but also to discover and gather their strengths. Lastly, to adapt to the changing social context, the school principal in the current period must have creative leadership to actively lead his school in taking on new challenges and changes (Farah, 2013).

Developing Leadership Competencies for Highschool Principals

Regarding the theory of leadership development, many authors have also raised different but consensual views on the diversity of activities such as training, seminars, forums, and cooperation between universities, research institutes with educational institutions in each locality. Little (1987) Lieberman, 1995; Loucks-Horsley et al., (1987) consider competency development as any activity undertaken - either in whole or in part - that enable school principals to improve their performance in their current or future role (Little, 1987, Lieberman, 1995, Loucks-Horsley et al., 1987). Paul Cobb and Ingvarson et al. believed that advanced learning should be viewed from both the requirements of the principals of high schools and the actual needs of society, which is meaningful for their professional development (Little, 1993, Ingvarson, et al, 2005, Lieberman & Miller, 1991). Guskey pointed out that the principal's participation in development/improvement and

compilation of textbooks, learning materials, educational programs, management of school/local education plans... are all valuable to their professional development (Guskey, 2000).

Both studies and practice show that it is necessary to provide formal training and retraining programs to develop the leadership capacity of principals following specific characteristics of local policies and cultures. Hilda Borko believes that classes and training courses inside and outside the school community or professional development seminars, discussions among colleagues after solving a difficult management situation from practice helps to develop school leadership competencies (Borko, 2004). Huber believes that, even though most principals have management experience to various degrees when they are appointed, they are not necessarily ready to meet the requirements of the 21st century in leading a specific school. Therefore, training programs offered to principals need to be developed based on the analysis of needs and contextual factors at each locality and each school. (Huber, 2004).

Through the analysis of the above perspectives, it can be seen that leadership development for school principals needs to follow a process that includes leadership development programs implemented by training institutions, while at the same time, there should be a self-training program of the principals themselves that adapts to the local policy and cultural context.

The Process of Developing Leadership Competencies for highschool Principals

Developing leadership competencies is progress, especially when modern principals have to reinvent themselves continuously to adapt to the changing environment, such as the need for the principal to mobilize and manage resources more effectively; or the need to lead the school to become an open and dynamic organization within the society. Therefore, effective leadership development is not limited to just one program, one course, or one stage, but needs to be developed in a combination of learning, training, and practice associated with school practice and social contexts. (Pont et al., 2008)

Pont et al. thinks that leadership development is best started with teachers, then continued with principal candidates; followed by pre-service training, and finished by training for the first year of the principal's term. In this way, continuing formal development takes advantage of the leaders' previous experience. They will possess a wealth of experience and a deep understanding of the needs of the job and how to do it effectively. New changes will allow core leaders to convey their experiences and skills to newer leaders while acquiring new knowledge and skills themselves as well as refreshing long-term knowledge that has not been applied through mentoring and guiding new peers in the principals' network (Pont et al, 2008, chapter 4)

Tony Bush argues that, in principle, there are two main strategies for identifying potential school leaders. The first strategy can be "self-nominated" and the second strategy is deciding on who is considered for promotion. (Bush, 2008, Chapter 5).

The leadership development process associated with a high school principal's career can be described in the diagram below:

Figure 2: The leadership development process associated with a high school principal's career

Step 1: Pre-service training

Regarding policy practice in Vietnam, potential teachers for leadership and management positions are mainly planned. In OECD countries, as well as in Vietnam, the most important criterion for becoming a school leader is to have a teaching background. (Pont et al, 2008, chapter 5; Bush, 2008, Chapter 5).

In Denmark, potential teachers pass a "trial course" of one or more modules of the Diploma of Leadership Education Program and continue to a full two-year course. In the Netherlands, teachers can take an orientation course on management, then create a personal development plan based on competency analysis and then receive further training. (Schleicher, 2012, Chapter 1). Singapore requires an intensive leadership qualification for principals who obtained the Diploma of Education Administration (DEA) in July 1984 (Bush and Chew 1999, Bush, 2008, chapter 4). Scotland offers a referral program for teachers who wish to be part of a leadership team (Schleicher, 2012, Chapter 1). In Ontario, Canada, leaders must complete a Principal's

Certificate program and must adhere to 60 hours of practical experience, including assuming leadership roles in their school with the supervision of a current principal and independently carry out leadership projects during that time (Bush, 2008, Chapter 5).

Participation in leadership development programs through courses has important implications, which can be illustrated by the following model::

Figure 2: Stylised example of career teacher and leadership development

(Source: Dr. Ben Jensen, Amélie Hunter, Tim Lambert, and Dr. Anna Clark, *INSIGHTS ASPIRING PRINCIPAL PREPARATION*, Australian Institute for Teaching and School Leadership, 2015, p.10).

Step 2: Trained for the first year as a school leader in school practice

Becoming familiar with leadership in school practice will be meaningful to new principals, as it helps them understand the complex realities of school leadership and builds their confidence to take on the role effectively. Bush et al. (2007) pointed out the importance of school leaders that actively develops personal leadership capacity through solving practical problems in school management (Bush et al, 2007).

Principals need support and training, especially during their first year in leadership roles, through participating in leadership training programs for newly appointed principals, which can help to familiarize them with all areas of work, school activities, and network building through which leaders can share their concerns. In the UK, the National Professional Standards Program (2009) is mandatory for leaders, targeting six key areas: Shaping the future; Learning and teaching; Developing yourself and working with others; Organizational management; Ensuring accountability; Strengthening the community (Bush, 2008). Ontario (Canada), Ireland, Northern Ireland, Scotland, and Victoria (Australia) all have relatively comprehensive training programs including introductory programs to support the early stages of leadership, provided by professional training facilities (Schleicher, 2012, Chapter 1). In the United States, there are a variety of programs that develop the leadership skills necessary for new principals to successfully lead high schools (Jensen et al., 2012).

Another way for new leaders to receive practical training is school leaders with years of experience acting as formal advisors providing ideas and advice, imparting experiences and their skills for newly appointed high school principals. At the same time, these long-term leaders also absorb new knowledge as well as refresh old knowledge that has not been applied for a long time through mentoring and guidance (Schleicher, 2012, chapter 1; Pont et al, 2008, chapter 4).

Step 3: Training through leadership practice at school

David Holman (2000) argues that it is necessary to approach “theory” and “practice” in a balanced way in developing the leadership capacity of principals (Holman, 2000). Empiricism has played an important role in the leadership career of high school principals, while also promoting the need for learning and professional development in general. However, that experience also raises questions about traditional authority and preparedness to adapt to new challenges to realize the organization's vision and values (Clarke et al., 2004).

Effective leadership development needs to be linked to the implementation of the school's mission in the local context. Since then, many different forms of leadership development are implemented in a personalized approach, while promoting the initiative and autonomy of managers themselves as they learn from their leadership activities, from their successes and failures, and from observing other local leaders. Burgoyne et al. (2004) make the point that the management and leadership style of school principals depends on specific situations, so it is not always the same, leading to the need for leadership development practices rather than applying a universal model for all principals (Burgoyne et al., 2004). In addition, the individual manager's contemplation in practical and specific contexts is very valuable. (Bolden, 2010).

The leadership training phase at the school is evaluated as a proactive and highly adaptive professional development activity. In the UK, training content is designed by taking into consideration individual contexts and school realities to meet the leadership development needs of principals during the first three years of their role (Bush and Glover, 2003).

Step 4: Cultivation through school leader network

According to Evans and Mohr (1999), leadership development for principals becomes effective when they participate in groups that engage in regular discussions. Local or non-local principal professional development networks such as the principals club model have the effect of motivating principals to go beyond their sometimes hypothetical experiences to expand their experiences or change their perceptions through analysis of challenging or controversial issues. It is also necessary to provide a safe environment in which principals can take risks, fail, learn and grow (Evans and Mohr, 1999).

Bush and Jackson argued that professional development takes place within and outside the school network with rich process strategies such as mentoring, coaching, school visiting, and discussing more likely to promote leadership learning than merely engaging with theories and researches (Bush and Jackson, 2002).

Bush and Glover's evaluation found out that connecting experiential learning, participating in a mentoring and coaching network is always highly valued by participating principals (Bush and Glover, 2005, Bush et al., 2007).

Herriot et al. (2002) report on the development of principal support groups in Kenya through the non-focused training program for primary school principals (PRISM). These groups are considered "central to the sustainability of good governance in schools" with the main purpose of (1) Forming forums for sharing ideas; (2) Co-developing school policies; (3) Solve management and leadership problems; (4) Find creative ways to generate additional income; (5) Develop staff; (6) Improve teaching efficiency (Herriot et al. (2002).

Principal networks within and outside of the local area can support leadership development within groups in the form of coaching and mentoring. Coaching can include both casual discussions as well as more organized meetings. That said, the practice provides a powerful new source of guidance for practicing leaders, as well as a framework for ongoing leadership development.

Step 5: Participate in training for subordinates or newly appointed school leaders

Mentoring and coaching for newly appointed school leaders are increasingly common in professional development. Although the terms are sometimes used interchangeably, it is most commonly understood as the activity in which a more experienced individual assists someone less experienced. In this form, training is used to assist individuals in performing a specific task to develop a skill or ability (Hobson and Sharp, 2005).

Further research on mentoring has shown it to be effective and has become a standard in principal evaluation in the US and UK. With experienced principals in the US, their responsibilities extend to assisting and advising a new principal in administrative activities. At the same time, the performance evaluation of a principal's deemed experience also includes the level of support he or she has for the newly appointed principal (The Wallace Foundation, 2012). A UK study found that high school principals value their mentoring role with newly appointed principals. (Luck, (2003). In his report on the New Zealand context, Stewart (2000) states that on-site professional development is most effectively underpinned by a link between the person himself and a leader outside the school, which is a systematic and practical form of reflection (Stewart, 2000). In the United States, since 2000, more than half of the states have enacted advisory requirements for newly appointed principals. NASBE (National Association of State Boards of Education) conducted a training program called "Entry-Year Program for Principals" in Ohio for school principals. The program requires all new principals to work with counselors for two years to officially receive their licensure (The Wallace Foundation, 2012).

Study methods

Research design

This study uses a non-experimental research design which is a survey method using a poll. The respondents to the survey are principals of public and private high schools in the province/city. The time to respond to a survey is about 15-30 minutes. The survey is combined with the method of retrospective documentation on the legal documents regulating the appointment of school principals in Vietnam.

Instruments of the study

A poll containing questions about the school leadership capacity of high school principals was designed and implemented by a research team from the Faculty of Education Management, University of Education, Vietnam National University, Hanoi. Respondents are asked to rate the level of achievement for each section on the Likert scale from the lowest level of 1 to the highest level of 5. In addition, the study also conducted interviews to gain information on local practices about the full implementation of the process and the steps in the process.

Research sample

The survey sample consisted of 295 principals of high schools in five provinces and cities: Quang Ninh, Hai Phong, Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh City, and Hue. Although the survey samples were not selected by random method, the samples were deliberately selected to ensure that there are provinces and cities in the North (Quang Ninh, Hanoi, Hai Phong), in the Central (Hue city) and the South of Vietnam (Ho Chi Minh City).

Bảng 1. Characteristics of the school leadership capacity survey sample (n=295)

Factors		Number	Percentage
Gender	Male	213	72.2%
	Female	82	27.8%
Province of employment	Quang Ninh	20	6,8%
	Hai Phong	57	26,1%
	Hanoi	99	33,6%
	Hue	19	6,4%
	Ho Chi Minh City	100	33,9%
Working experience (years)	<10 years	18	6.1%
	10-20 years	117	39.7%
	>20 years	160	54.2%
Time working as the school principal (years)	<1 year	6	0.02%
	1-10 years	185	62.7%
	>10 years	104	35.2%
Total		295	100%

Findings and discussion

In Vietnam, policies on training, cultivating, and coaching leadership and management competencies for high school principals have been legalized since 2005 by the 2005 Education Law (No. 38/2005/QH11, June 14, 2005) and most recently Circular No. 32/2020/TT-BGDĐT dated June 15, 2020, promulgating the Charter of junior high schools, high schools, and multi-level high schools, effective November 1, 2020.

Specifically, Education Law 2005: Article 54, Clause 2 stipulates that "Principals of schools in the national education system must be trained and fostered in school management skills", Education Law 2019, effective Effective from July 1, 2020: Article 56, Clause 2 stipulates that "School principals under the national education system must be trained and fostered in school management skills and meet the standards of principals". In addition, Decree 101/2017/ND-CP issued on September 1, 2017: Article 18, Clause 2 stipulates that the program to foster state management knowledge must be administered to an individual before that individual is appointed to leadership and management positions. Circular No. 32/2020/TT-BGDĐT, Article 11, Clause 1 stipulates: "Principal... **self-study and self-improve** to improve professional and management capacity; **To be trained** to improve qualifications, to foster professional skills and to receive rights as

prescribed by law. Thus, policies on training and cultivating leadership capacity for high school principals in Vietnam are also implemented according to the process associated with the principal's career.

The following results show the assessment of the principals of the high schools on the training and retraining practices of high school principals.

Table 2. Evaluation of training and retraining practices of Vietnamese high school principals

Order	Factor	Strongly agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly disagree (1)	Total
Step 1	Pre-service training	122	143	20	9	1	295
		41.4%	48.5%	6.8%	3.1%	0.3%	100%
Step 2	Trained for the first year as a school leader in school practice	135	124	27	8	1	295
		45.8%	42.0%	9.2%	2.7%	0.3%	100%
Step 3	Training through leadership practice at school	130	137	24	3	1	295
		44.1%	46.4%	8.1%	1.0%	0.3%	100%
Step 4	Cultivation through school leader network	112	150	27	5	1	295
		38.0%	50.8%	9.2%	1.7%	0.3%	100%
Step 5	Participate in training for subordinates or newly appointed school leaders	129	131	32	2	1	295
		43.7%	44.4%	10.8%	0.7%	0.3%	100%

Out of 259 principals asked about their agreement with the 5-step process of leadership development of high school principals: >80% strongly agree and agree with all steps in the process, especially with the high percentage of strongly agree with step 2 “Training for the first year in school leadership practice” (45.8%) and step 3 “Training through practical leadership at school” (44.1%). However, there are also from 0.3% to 1.7% of the participants that strongly disagree with the proposed steps. A further survey on the need for principals to develop from teachers showed that 41% strongly agree with the opinion.

The results of interviews with principals of public high schools show that the majority approves of the principal development process from teachers because that maturation process allows the principal to understand key activities in the school, understand both individuals and collective teachers as well as the local culture.

However, the pre-service training process has only been carried out recently and is locality-dependent. Before that, principals can be appointed and then be trained in management skills and self-study through mostly their work.

Pre-service training

Table 3: Assessment of the status of pre-service training of the principals of Vietnamese high schools

Order	Factor	Level of Necessity				Level of implementation			
		N	Mean	St. Dev	Std. Error or Mean	N	Mean	St. Dev	Std. Error or Mean

1	Bachelor's Degree in School Management and Leadership	295	4.22	.829	.048	295	3.17	1.109	.065
2	Training bachelor's degree in pedagogy and supplementing Certificates in school management and leadership	295	4.10	.881	.051	295	3.22	1.136	.066
3	Postgraduate training (Master, Ph.D.) in School Management and Leadership	295	3.96	.903	.053	295	3.19	1.067	.062
4	Training towards achieving school leadership standards	295	4.30	.675	.039	295	3.18	1.056	.062
5	Training and developing school leaders before being appointed	295	4.23	.766	.045	295	3.21	1.065	.062
6	Encourage potential/planned school teachers to voluntarily improve their graduate training in school leadership	295	4.19	.738	.043	295	3.26	1.046	.061
7	Selecting potential school leaders through pre-service training	295	4.11	.751	.044	295	3.20	1.049	.061

The survey results above show that principals highly appreciate the necessity of pre-service training on school leadership for potential teachers for the position of Principal. All of the above forms are evaluated at a very necessary and necessary level, with (Lowest Mean = 3.96, Highest Mean = 4.30).

Regarding the level of performance of pre-service training on school leadership for potential teachers for the position of Principal, principals rated it as average with a Mean in the range of 3.13 to 3.26. University-level pedagogical training and additional certificates in school management and leadership were also appreciated by principals more than other forms, with a mean of 3.22. In conclusion, it is still necessary to continue to develop additional training and cultivating programs for school leaders when they officially become principals to meet the increasing requirements of Vietnam's educational environment in the current context.

Interview regarding pre-service training for school principals:

- Mr. Nguyen T- Director of Department of Education and Training, Thua Thien Hue province: Currently, we do not have a separate training program for principals. At present, most principals are appointed to undertake management work, then go on to train in a management capacity and attend postgraduate training courses on educational management. If principals are better prepared in terms of knowledge and leadership skills through pre-appointment training courses, they will work more effectively.

Trained for the first year as a school leader in school practice

Table 4: Assessment of the training situation of first-year principals of Vietnamese high schools

T T	Training method for first-year principals	Level of Necessity				Level of implementation			
		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
1	School leadership training program by	295	4.32	.742	.043	295	3.20	1.122	.065

	knowledgeable local school leaders								
2	Training program in school leadership by a network of senior and experienced school leaders	295	4.25	.749	.044	295	3.23	1.088	.063
3	Counseling by a local leader or school leader with seniority and experience in educational leadership	295	4.14	.747	.043	295	3.15	1.039	.060
4	Counseling by expert school leadership and school knowledge	295	4.17	.790	.046	295	3.16	1.036	.060
5	Counseling by senior and experienced administrators, teachers/staff of the school itself	295	4.09	.813	.047	295	3.14	1.041	.061

The above survey results show that principals highly appreciate the need for principals to be trained in the first year as school leaders through school practice. This is very evident in all forms, which are rated as very necessary and necessary with the average score (Lowest Mean = 4.09, Highest Mean = 4.32).

Regarding the level of implementation of the training for the first-year principals as school leaders in school practice, the principals' rating of necessity is at an average level in the range of 3.14 to 3.20, and there was no statistically significant difference in the ratings between the forms. However, the option of through the training programs has a higher average score: 'Implement a School Leadership Training Program consisting of multiple elective modules for new principals appointed for the first time by a network of senior and experienced school leaders' have a mean of 3.23, and 'Implement a School Leadership Training Program for the newly appointed Principal, first appointed by local leaders and knowledgeable about smart schools' have a mean of 3.20.

Training through leadership practice at school

Table 5: Assessment of the current situation of training through leadership practice at schools by the principals of Vietnamese high schools

Order	Factor	Level of Necessity				Level of implementation			
		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
1	Training at undergraduate and postgraduate levels (Master, Ph.D.) in a leadership capacity	295	4.05	.817	.048	295	3.24	1.085	.063
2	Develop school leadership through annual professional development activities	295	4.18	.684	.040	295	3.16	.988	.058
3	Develop school	295	4.14	.747	.043	295	3.15	1.004	.058

	leadership as required by the specific context of achieving the goal at the national, regional, local, or school level								
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Compared to other forms in the development process associated with the career of high school principals in Vietnam, leadership development associated with practice at schools has a special advantage due to cultural and policy relevance.

Through the opinion of the principals, all three forms of leadership development through school practice were assessed as quite necessary with the mean ranging from 4.05 to 4.18 with a statistically significant difference.

Training forms based on the school's leadership practices are generally still highly appreciated with inherent advantages due to both policy and cultural factors in the context of schools in Vietnam. In many professional fields (including school leaders) practical experience is especially valued.

Recently, many research projects have been conducted to find solutions to effectively support various forms of training in Vietnam. In November 2018, the authors at the University of Education - VNU published a study on leadership and management skills of high school principals, along with some recommendations that emphasized the need to develop training programs by address, taking into account participants (principals of high schools, educational administrators and teachers who are subject to planning management positions) in specific locations. Leadership development programs should focus on the context of the local community and the school, taking into account local economic, cultural, and policy realities (Nguyen and Duong, 2018).

Interview regarding training through leadership practice at school:

- Ms. Tran Thi Hai Y- Principal of Tran Phu High School - Hoan Kiem - Hanoi: Compared to many localities, Hanoi is quite open and dynamic. I appreciate the school's forms of leadership training because they link theory with practice right in the process of principals working in their leadership roles. This will help us to be more active in both the role of participators and the role of organizing forms of leadership training for ourselves as well as for key staff and teachers in schools and school clusters.

Cultivation through school leader network

Table 6: Assessment of the current situation of Cultivation through school leader network of Vietnamese high schools

Order	Factor	Level of Necessity				Level of implementation			
		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
1	Participating in leadership development activities for principals organized by the provincial Department of Education and Training	295	4.23	.769	.045	295	3.24	1.115	.065
2	Participating in the Informal Leadership Development Network of Principals	295	4.14	.719	.042	295	3.21	1.043	.061

For the two forms of fostering in the network of school leaders inside and outside of respective localities, they are highly appreciated for their necessity with reliable and meaningful statistical data. This form of training is highly appreciated for its flexibility and mobility in terms of time and place of implementation and especially reflects the characteristics of the local context and the school. In Vietnam, leadership development activities such as high school clubs will be organized by the Department of Education and Training of that locality (this division is also by the government according to regulations on the management level), in addition, many informal leadership development networks of Principals have also been established in localities with

similar conditions and contexts. These networks operate under the model of an independent and voluntary professional organization with topics always associated with school leadership practices.

However, through the data obtained with reliability and statistical significance, there are also differences in the assessment between the level of necessity and the level of implementation, namely (mean=3.24; 3,21) are all average. Compared with other forms of leadership development, participation in the informal leadership development network of principals is quite new in Vietnam, and in terms of mechanisms and policies, it is not yet complete. Specifically, the principal network operates in a voluntary spirit, leading to effectiveness is dependent on the level of dynamism of each locality, organizational capacity, and activeness of school principals. In many other localities in Vietnam, these clubs operate in a formalistic way, the organization of the network of principals is not high, and there is a lack of influential and reputable individuals to lead.

Interview regarding school leaders' network:

- Mr. Pham Ngoc D - Principal of Hien Da High School - Phu Tho: Participation in the informal leadership development network of Principals is essential to us. However, in my locality, as in many other places, the activities of the principal's club are still spontaneous, the topics for each meeting are unclear and inconsistent. Many principals are also hesitant to share difficulties due to their leadership capacity limitations, so the network of principals has not yet become a forum for professional leadership support for members.

Participate in training for subordinates or newly appointed school leaders

Table 7: Assessment of the Participate in training for subordinates or newly appointed school leaders of Vietnamese high schools

Order	Factor	Level of Necessity				Level of implementation			
		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
1	Strategies that develop teachers and school administrators into the position of Principals of schools and localities.	295	4.38	.712	.041	295	3.29	1.117	.065
2	Selecting, providing on-the-job training, recommending participation in fostering leadership development sessions for potential candidates for the position of Principal	295	4.28	.714	.042	295	3.25	1.068	.062
3	Formal or informal coaching and mentoring for newly appointed Principals	295	4.19	.706	.041	295	3.18	1.066	.062

The obtained data is reliable and statistically significant, showing the evaluation of the forms of fostering school leadership capacity to the necessary level through training for subordinates or newly appointed school leaders. The development and appointment of principals from teachers at the school themselves help candidates gain practical experience in each specific school context, quickly eliminating the initial confusion to adapt to both new and new roles. new working environment. The standard deviation is also low (< 0.714), indicating that there is not much difference in opinion among participants.

Similar to the evaluation results of many other forms of leadership capacity building, the performance evaluation results are average with reliable data. However, with a standard deviation of > 1,066, it shows that the differences in opinion are statistically significant, reflecting differences in policies as well as culture in each locality.

There are gaps between expectations and actual performance of each form of leadership development because performance is influenced by too many subjective and objective factors in each school.

Interview regarding coaching for potential school leaders or first-year principals:

- Mr. Pham Ngoc D - Principal of Hien Da High School - Phu Tho:

As a principal, I highly appreciate the above-mentioned forms of training because it utilizes local resources and links leadership development with school development. However, I want to mention the difficulty in implementation and the efficiency of the implementation. These activities depend on the current principal's level of authorization and openness, but are the principals willing to take action? Most principals may support the professional development of teachers in their schools. However, staff leadership development is another matter because the notion that leadership is for managers denies the opportunity for teachers, even planned leaders, to learn leadership skills. With that in mind, specific strategies to develop teachers into leadership positions are almost nonexistent, from lack of strategic planning to support, enabling teachers to participate in training courses, resulting in very few forms of school leadership development. Teachers are also afraid of expressing their desire to develop and be promoted, so in the preparation of teachers who are subject to planning for management positions, the preparation of competent leadership for themselves is the most lacking.

Recommendation:

It can be seen that leadership development for high school principals in Vietnam is now regulated in legal documents since 2005 and the process to develop professional capacity for public school principals. The establishment often begins with the development of the professional achievement of teachers with the potential and aspirations to become leaders.

However, to develop a teacher with the potential to become a high school leader follows a 5-step process that ties in to their career in school leadership practices and training in a career networking system. together with their participation and continuing training program in Vietnam at present has not been fully implemented and has not met the practical requirements.

The survey results of 295 public high school principals of 5 provinces and cities representing 3 regions in North, Central, and South Vietnam show the lack of support in developing school principals in Vietnam. In terms of policy and culture, principals appointed for the first time in their first year of assignment have not yet received effective support through the career path. For example, local government support is not specified, and it is not yet common to establish a network of principals in each locality to train and advise new principals. Personally, the senior principals are aware of the mission as well as ready to train and support the new principal to take on the task, but currently, there is no clear policy regarding functions, duties, and rights for principal advisors. In addition, some senior principals do not realize the opportunity to continue developing their leadership career through training new principals.

Thus, to develop leadership capacity for high school principals in Vietnam according to the above 5-step process, it is necessary to do the following 3 tasks shortly:

(i) leading educational leadership institutions should develop at least three training programs including an intensive training program for potential teachers, a pre-service training program for first-time principals, and a training program that supports first-time principals in their first year. These training programs should be considered as a mandatory requirement, with particular attention to local policies and regional cultures,

(ii) the local government and the Department of Education and Training need to build a network of principals with clear regulations on functions and duties to support newly appointed principals and support each other; associate the responsibility of fostering new principals with representatives of local authorities, such as vice-chairmen of the provincial/city or district/province People's Committees in charge of culture and education.

(iii) there should be formal regulation regarding principals involved in the training of newly appointed principals and the assessment of the professional progress of newly appointed principals.

Conclusion

This case study presented the practice of training and fostering management and leadership capacity of principals of high schools in Vietnam according to the path associated with their careers. Practical experiences resonate with each other and the 'participant as co-researchers approach allows participants to add to the depth and reliability of data that point to inherent complexity. in transferring theories on training and fostering school leadership capacity in the practical context of culture and policy in Vietnam. Survey participants (survey subjects) gave their opinions on both the necessity and implementation level of the stages of training and fostering school leadership capacity and the distances from theory to practice.

The general assessment is that training and fostering leadership capacity in stages associated with the career of high school principals is necessary to help principals prepare for school leadership, although the level of implementation of this process in practice is still between average and below average.

Policies on training, fostering as well as developing principals should generally be approached from the practical needs at grassroots levels, with school principals as participants. The creation of trust and a safe space for personal reflection and growth can underpin effective capacity building for change and improvement, at the system and school level as well as the leadership and the pedagogical level. Adoption of a network of principals

in local administrations based on local strengths and resources that interact with school leadership practices can increase willingness to take risks and try new approaches to address ongoing challenges. It is also from this foundation of trust and support that the support network between successive principals can be developed and perfected as a tiered shared leadership training model that is effectively used by the research school, such as the network of high school principals in Hanoi in the form of principals' clubs.

Even so, the complexity of sharing development direction and resources at the grassroots level should also be taken into account to avoid competing priorities and misunderstandings, which is important in ensuring cooperation and efficiency between principals, and by extension, their schools.

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